

were exposed to *Diopsis thoracica* (25 males and 25 females) in a wooden cage for 3 days to allow egg laying. The eggs laid per pot were counted. Ten days after the eggs hatched, deadhearts were

counted.

The most eggs and deadhearts were recorded on plants 20-40 DT (see table). In both varieties, 30-day-old plants recorded the highest number of eggs and

deadhearts. The rate of deadheart development was fastest in 10- to 30-day-old plants. Virtually no eggs were laid or deadhearts developed on 60-day-old plants. ■

Effect of intensity of light on the predacious green mirid bug

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The green mirid bug *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis* Reuter is a predator on the eggs and early-stage nymphs of brown planthoppers (BPH) and green leafhoppers (GLH). Its number is large in the light traps and in the field during September-October when the activity of BPH and GLH is very high.

The effect of light intensity on attracting this predator was studied using incandescent lights of different intensities from October 1980 to February

Mirid bugs trapped with lights of 4 intensities, 1980-81, Tamil Nadu, India.

	Mirid bugs trapped (no.)				Total
	15 watts	40 watts	60 watts	100 watts	
October	543	1156	1570	3670	6939
November	11	120	156	474	761
December	9	75	48	194	326
January	1	16	42	66	125
February	-	1	5	7	13
Total	564	1368	1821	4411	-

1981 (see table).

The mirid bug was very active during October, when the numbers of BPH and GLH were also high (BPH 21,174; GLH 11,928). Predator incidence was positively correlated with populations of BPH and GLH. The mirid bug population then declined and reached very low levels during February, when activity of

the two insect pests also was low (BPH 129, GLH 17).

With increased light intensity, there was a corresponding increase in the catch of pests and predators. But high wattage in the light trap removed bio-control agents from rice fields. Rice pests can be monitored with low wattage bulbs. ■

Esterases and malathion resistance in brown planthopper

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The 4th and 5th instars of the brown planthopper (BPH) were used in the bioassay to determine the effect of *S,S,S*-tributyl phosphorotrithioate (DEF), an esterase inhibitor, on toxicity of malathion and of two other organophosphorus insecticides against a malathion-resistant (R) strain of BPH. DEF enhanced malathion toxicity 20 times, methyl parathion toxicity 6 times, and parathion 11 times (see table).

This implies that detoxification mediated by these esterases is associated with insecticide resistance in the BPH.

Spectrophotometric determination of esterase activity in BPH males with different levels of malathion resistance showed a linear relationship between esterase activity and log-resistance ratio (see figure). Similar reactions have been reported for the green rice leafhopper and the smaller BPH. ■

Effect of DEF on susceptibility to 3 insecticides of a malathion-resistant (R) brown planthopper strain, Taiwan.

Insecticide	RR ^a	LC ₅₀ (mg/ml)		SR ^b
		Alone	With DEF	
Malathion	484	11.13	0.56	19.9
Methyl parathion	35	1.00	0.17	5.9
Parathion	141	2.67	0.24	11.1

^aResistance ratio = LC₅₀ of resistant strain divided by LC₅₀ of susceptible strain. ^bSynergistic ratio = LC₅₀ of insecticide divided by LC₅₀ of insecticide with DEF (*S,S,S*-tributyl phosphorotrithioate).

Resistance ratio

α -naphthyl acetate (μ mol/ 10 min per mg).